

Virtual calculation of the B-value allowables of notched composite laminates

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1. Analytical prediction of the notched strength based on three ply properties

The design of composite structures relies on the accurate determination of design allowables, which are statistically based material parameters that take into account manufacturing, geometrical and microstructure variability.

There is the need to develop alternatives to the experimental material characterization process. A methodology to predict the B-value of notched composite laminates using an analytical framework [1] to estimate the notched strength of multidirectional carbon-epoxy laminates is proposed.

The analytical framework is based on only three ply properties [2-5]:

- the longitudinal Young's modulus, E_1
- the longitudinal strength, X
- the longitudinal crack resistance curve, R -curve.

The model is particularly useful for preliminary design and optimization.

2. UQ&M framework and case study

The variability associated with the determination of the ply properties and the geometry of the specimens is accounted for to compute the B-basis allowable, which is a statistically-based design allowable defined as the 95% lower confidence bound on the tenth percentile of a specified population of measurements.

An IM7/8552 [90/0/-45/45]_{3s} quasi isotropic laminate with a central circular hole loaded in tension was used to exemplify the methodology.

	E1 [GPa]	X ^T [MPa]	R _{SS} [N/mm]	Radius [mm]	Width [mm]
Mean	171.42	2323.47	206.75	r	w
Std	2.38	127.45	26.64	2% x r	2% x w

3. Validation

Errors below 12% between the prediction and experimental results were obtained. The proposed methodology allows not only to obtain good predictions of the average notched strengths but also the expected statistical distribution and corresponding estimation of the B-basis allowables.

5. Concluding remarks

The proposed framework is validated successfully for the open-hole tension specimens. The framework can be used to quickly generate design charts for notched specimens to assist engineers during the initial stages of the design process.

The UQ&M framework can be extended to other notched configurations, provided the stress distribution and energy release rate are known for those geometries and loading conditions.

4. Generation of design charts

The framework can be used to generate statistically representative design charts [2] and compare the performance of different layouts and materials in a preliminary stage of the design process. These tools are particularly useful for design engineers and would otherwise be infeasible to attain as they require a large number of testing or time-consuming finite element simulations to be performed.

References

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